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Enabling cost reduction on Alkali Electrolyzers by Innovative Plastic Compounds

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Abstract

Facing the ramp up of the electrolyzer market with quite ambitious targets of >30GW Power in EU by 2030, the costs of the systems need to be reduced for efficient business scenarios. According to a prediction in the IEA – Global Hydrogen Review 2022, AWE (Alkali Water Electrolyzer) will be producing almost 2/3 of green hydrogen by 2030, due to that it is essential having a closer look at the components of an AWE like the frame of the stack which distributes the media, withstands the inner pressure of up to 35 bars and gives the system its shape and rigidity. Today, this frame is made of either multicomponent materials containing quite expensive polymers and/or using a supportive metal ring. This frame accounts for 14-20% of the costs of a AWE stack according to Zao et. al. [1]. MOCOM Compounds investigated the market and developed a polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) compound containing a filler which indicates to be resistant against 30% potassium hydroxide solution for usage in AWE frames and insulator plates. During the development, the temperature resistance of the new composition was tested compared to unfilled PPS, glass-fiber filled PPS, as well as PPSU and PSU. To simplify storage testing, 30% NaOH solution was used instead of 30% KOH solution based on a positive pre-investigation of comparability. A stable behavior at 90°C in 30% NaOH over 672h was observed without degradation of the mechanical performance in modulus, tensile strength, elongation at break and even Charpy unnotched impact performance. This was not the case for PPS with glass-fiber. Starting at a higher mechanical level, a continuous degradation and drop in performance were observed and documented for Tedur L PPS GF30 (standard glass fiber). The new Tedur L PPS 4030 NC1049-24 compound enables to make an AWE frame out of a 1K solution with comprehensive cost reduction potential of up to 40% in the raw material at elevated creep performance. It also enables the chance for a 2K solution. Tedur L PPS 4030 NC1049-24 can be co-injected and combined with other Tedur L PPS compounds with glass fibers and/or mineral fillers for structural improvement and further cost reduction for each frame. This can mean in total a cost benefit of more than 50% in raw material costs.

AWE electrolyzers will continue to dominate the market with a market share ~55% by 2050, according to De Nora

Green hydrogen production by technology (M tons)

Figure 1: Source: De Nora website; Goldman Sachs – ‘Carbonomics’; IEA

Introduction

Alkaline Water Electrolysis (AWE) is a well-known and established technology for the production of hydrogen today. The share of AWEs accounts currently to more than 2/3 of the total hydrogen production capacity and is going to be more than 50% expected by 2050 [2].

That means the further development and cost reduction of the capex of alkali electrolyzers is crucial for achieving the ambitious goals of the EU to reach more than 30 GW of power by 2030. A key component of these systems is the stack frame, which distributes the media, withstands internal pressures of up to 35 bars, and provides the system with its shape and rigidity. The frame accounts for 14-20% of the costs of an AWEL stack [1]. Today's solutions include metal frames, metal-rubber/plastic combinations like the Zentrum für Sonnenenergie- und Wasserstoff-Forschung Baden-Württemberg (ZSW) is using it [3] or thermoplastic PSU and PPSU solutions e.g. promoted by BASF [4]. Using thermoplastic solutions like PPSU or PSU is rather expensive from a material cost perspective. The investigation's aim is to significantly reduce today's prices to achieve a real cost benefit. That means that MOCOM Compounds GmbH & Co. KG wants to follow another path and conducted an in-depth investigation to determine whether there is potential for lower material costs and to identify the limitations of the currently industrialized compounds available.

Figure 2: AWEL Stack & simplified schematic Frame Design (generated with ChatGPT)

1. Scientific Approach

MOCOM Compounds GmbH is a provider of a variety of standard and special polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) compounds. PPS itself is resistant against KOH over a longer period and temperature range why it is for example used as part of AWE diaphragms [6] [7]. PPS has a glass transition temperature (T_g) of around 90 °C. Temperature above T_g has a high influence on the mechanical performance of the material in terms of stiffness and strength in an unfilled compound. Following graphs, figure 3 and 4, show the performance drop of unfilled PPS between 80-120 °C. However, the E-modulus and tensile strength of PSU and PPSU are rather stable up to 150 °C.

Figure 3: Absolute values of PPS unfilled at 23 - 120°C

Figure 4: Retention of PPS unfilled at 23 - 120°C

Although PPS itself is resistant to KOH over a longer period, it is still a semicrystalline material and shows significant performance benefits against PSU and PPSU in terms of creep. Figure 5 shows the creep performance of PPS unfilled compared to PSU and PPSU. Unfilled PPS performs 6 times better than PSU/PPSU in terms of creep behavior.

Figure 5: Creep comparison of PPS unfilled with PSU and PPSU unfilled [8]

Normally, E-glass fibers (GF) are used for the reinforcement of PPS compounds. This also brings additional cost benefits as glass fiber is less expensive compared to raw PPS. Nevertheless, PPS glass fiber filled is not a solution for alkaline water electrolyzer frames which are in contact with 30% potassium hydroxide (KOH) at higher pressure (up to 35 bars), hydrogen, oxygen and temperatures between 80 to 105 °C. This is because standard E-glass fibers are attacked by 30% KOH over time [5]. Figure 6 illustrates this effect.

Figure 6: SEM images at a magnification of 300 of the fractured surface of (A) unaged PPS-40%GF, and (B) PPS-40%GF exposed to 30 wt% KOH at 90°C for 61 days [5]

This necessitated the identification of a filler capable of reinforcing the PPS compound to endure higher mechanical forces at elevated temperatures above 80 to 90°C, while also exhibiting chemical resistance to the aforementioned media.

Consequently, MOCOM Compounds GmbH searched the market for fibers. On the way, several options came up and were tested like alkali resistant (AR)-glass fibers [9] or basalt fibers. AR-Fibers are used for concrete reinforcement at pH-Values of 13 [10].

Besides the mechanical performance in the system, the cost structure needs to be evaluated as well. Ideally, the cost of the filler are below the raw polymer price of PPS.

2. Experiments/Calculations/Simulations

As the accessibility and capacity for storage in 30% KOH at elevated temperatures was very limited, NaOH was used as testing solution. Potassium and sodium are neighbors in the periodic system and show similar properties, furthermore, there is more testing capacity in the market. In Table 1 you can see a comparison of the solutions based on potassium and sodium hydroxide. This comparison was the base for comparative storage tests in 30% KOH vs. 30% NaOH at 90°C for 672h.

Table 1: Comparison of KOH & NaOH based on the periodic system and density of the 30% solution

		30% KOH / potassium	30%NaOH / sodium
Density	g/mL*	1,281	1,328
Atom weight	kg/dm ³	0,86	0,91
Atom size	pm	220	180

*<https://www.periodensystem-online.de/index.php?id=lists&form=Dichtewerte&sst=5>

Further investigation started with Tedur L 9105-1, a PPS GF30, and a 30% alkaline resistant (AR)-glass fiber filled PPS compound. The mechanical values before and after storage in NaOH were compared for both grades. For further understanding of the behavior, microscopic images of the fractured area were taken.

With this procedure E-glass fibers, AR-glass fibers and other fillers have been evaluated. A series of additional tests were conducted on the most promising compound to assess its mechanical performance at elevated temperatures ranging from 80 to 100 °C which is the

typical operating window for alkaline water electrolyzers. In the end, based on several assumptions, a cost calculation is done to convince the reader that the potential of MOCOM Compounds GmbH approach can be highly beneficial, which contributes to a simplified cost-optimized system and reducing investment costs.

3. Results

Figure 7 illustrates the degradation of Tedur L 9105-1 (PPS GF30) in 30% KOH on the left side in vibrant purple and 30% NaOH on the right side in deep purple. Based on this, the influence of 30% NaOH on the PPS compound was found to be approximately equivalent to 30% KOH, meaning that storage in NaOH can be used for further tests. However, it still seems that 30% KOH has a greater influence on the notched impact performance than 30% NaOH, as further testing of NaOH has shown.

Figure 7: Comparison of the degradation of PPS GF30 in 30% NaOH (right) vs. 30% KOH (left)

Table 2, column “Before storage”, shows mechanical properties of the best performing AR-glass fiber (30weight%) PPS compound and standard PPS GF30. In total four different AR-fibers were investigated. The AR-glass fiber filled PPS shows a performance not as good as standard PPS GF30 but it seems like decent values for further investigation.

Table 2: Mechanical comparison of PPS GF30 and PPS AR-GF 30 before and after storage in 30% NaOH

		PPS + GF30		PPS + 30% AR-GF	
	Unit	Tedur L 9105-1 NC		Tedur L PPS 5030 NC1089-23	
		Before storage	Retention after storage in 30% NaOH, 90°C, 672h	Before storage	Retention after storage in 30% NaOH, 90°C, 672h
Flexural Modulus	MPa	10500	100%	8900	71%
Flexural Strength	MPa	245	100%	168	74%
Flex Strain/Deflection	%	2,5	98%	2,0	129%
Tensile Modulus	MPa	11900	92%	8490	86%
Tensile Strength	MPa	177	94%	115	64%
Elongation at break	%	2,32	86%	1,8	83%
Charpy unnotched	kJ/m ²	55,6	83%	20,6	58%

As a next step, storage in 30% NaOH at 90°C for 672h was done on PPS GF30 and PPS AR-GF30. This test showed a significant degradation of both materials. Although, the standard PPS GF30 performed much better than the AR-GF Type. This was quite astonishing given that the fiber should be more resistant. The degradation of Tedur L 9105-1 was between 8% - 17%, whereas that of Tedur L PPS 5030 (AR-GF Type) was between 14% - 42%. This indicates that there might be another problem. After certain investigations, it turned out that the bonding of the AR-GF in the polymer is worse than expected. Figure 8 shows that the breaking lines of the samples are totally different under a microscope. Tedur L 9105-1 (PPS GF30) has a very uneven breaking line compared to Tedur L PPS 5030. The fibers of the PPS 30% AR-GF are pulled out of the matrix as shown by the straight break line in (C) and (D). This indicates a bad connection between fiber and polymer. This has been discussed with the fiber producers to improve it beforehand. Nevertheless, no improvement could be seen.

Figure 8: Break area after Storage; A: Tedur L 9105-1 (PPS GF30); B: Detail of (A); C: Tedur L PPS 5030 (PPS AR-GF30); D:Detail of (C)

Further investigations identified another filler that appears to be highly resistant to KOH/NaOH. As in Table 3 stated, this filler reinforces the PPS compound in case of the E-modulus but weakens the tensile strength and Charpy impact at 23°C. The results may differ at elevated temperatures and under chemical load. However, those results are not available yet. Storage in 30% NaOH shows that the mechanical retention level is 100% after storage. There is no degradation.

Table 3: Mechanical performance of Tedur L PPS 4030 using a special KOH/NaOH resistant Filler

		PPS unfilled	PPS + GF30		PPS + 30% special-GF	
	Unit		Tedur L 9105-1 NC		Tedur L PPS 4030 NC1049-24	
		Before storage	Before storage	Retention after Storage in 30% NaOH, 90°C,672h	Before storage	Retention after Storage in 30% NaOH, 90°C,672h
Flexural Modulus	MPa	3900	10500	100%	5830	100%
Flexural Strength	MPa	130	245	100%	90	96%
Flex Strain/Deflection	%	-	2,5	98%	2,36	96%
Tensile Modulus	MPa	4000	11900	92%	5580	85-100%*
Tensile Strength	MPa	90	177	94%	63,5	100%
Elongation at break	%	3	2,32	86%	2	125%
Charpy unnotched	kJ/m ²	-	55,6	83%	14,6	100%

*based on one time testing with small statistics, further investigations are under way.

Additional experiments were conducted to compare the mechanical performance at elevated temperatures. These show some cut backs in terms of mechanical performance. Tensile testing was performed at 80°C and 100°C. Under certain conditions, the mechanical performance is weaker as shown in figure 9 and figure 10.

Figure 9: Tensile testing at 80°C & 100°C of PPS GF, PPS special filler, PSU and PPSU

Figure 10: Tensile testing at 80°C & 100°C of PPS GF, PPS special filler, PSU and PPSU

One of the key benefits of this special KOH resistant filler is, that it reduces the cost of the compound like glass fibers. Due the fact that the filler is cheaper than the polymer. That means, as of today, May 2025, the price for 1kg of compound at a 3to production and delivery is at about 11 €/kg and for 20to at 9,50 €/kg. PPS GF30 is at 10,50 €/kg for 3to and 9,25 €/kg at 20to. Comparing these prices to PSU or PPSU a cost reduction up to 40% can be achieved, already considering the lower density of PSU and PPSU compared to the PPS Compound. Some assumptions have been done in table 4 to generate a cost overview for a stack with a diameter of 1 m and 250 cells. The calculations was made either based on a 1 component frame made of the PPS with KOH resistant filler or as a 2 component solution using the PPS KOH resistant filler for the areas where it is in contact with the potassium hydroxide and an industrial PPS with 65% glass fiber plus mineral filled grade like Tedur L 9217-1 U for the rest of the frame compared to a PSU and PPSU frame.

Example of a calculation for the 1K & 2K frame solution:

Table 4: Example calculation of the costs for raw material of AWEL 1K and 2K frame and a stack consisting of 250 frames

Raw Material density:	Einheit		Raw Material Price (20to):*	Einheit	
Tedur L PPS 4030 NC1049-24	[g/cm ³]	1,58	Tedur L PPS 4030 NC1049-24	[€/kg]	9,5
Tedur L 9217-1 U BK0002-00**	[g/cm ³]	1,98	Tedur L 9217-1 U BK0002-00**	[€/kg]	4,9
PSU	[g/cm ³]	1,24	PSU	[€/kg]	18
PPSU	[g/cm ³]	1,29	PPSU	[€/kg]	20

Frame Size*:			Stack level:		
Outer Ø	[cm]	100	Frames per Stack*	[pcs]	250
Inner Ø	[cm]	75	Volume per Stack	[cm ³]	858,593
Thickness	[cm]	1	V/Stack = V/Frame x pcs/Stack		
Volume of Frame	[cm ³]	3,434	KOH resistant part of Frame		
V = (A _{outer} - A _{inner}) x Thickness & A = π x r ²			**Non KOH resistant part of Frame		
			50%		
			50%		

Raw Material Price of the 1K Frames:		
Tedur L PPS 4030 NC1049-24	[€]	12,887,5
PSU	[€]	19.163,8
PPSU	[€]	22.151,7

vs. Tedur

-32,75%

-41,82%

Raw Material Price of the 2K Frames:		
Tedur L PPS 4030 NC1049-24	[€]	6.443,75
**Tedur L 9217-1 U BK0002-00	[€]	4.165,04
Tedur 2K Frame	[€]	10.608,8
PSU	[€]	19.163,8
PPSU	[€]	22.151,7
€ = V/Stack x ρ x €/kg		

vs. Tedur

-44,64%

-52,11%

*assumptions

**Non KOH resistant part of the Frame

As shown in the calculation, there is a significant cost reduction for AWE frames possible. More than 50% cost reduction is possible for a multi component solution and around 40% if a 1K solution is used.

The investigation revealed that finding a reinforcing filler for PPS with KOH resistance at a beneficial pricing is not an easy task. Since more test capacities are available at reasonable prices for NaOH than for KOH, it was investigated whether NaOH can also be used as a media.

It was shown that NaOH solution has a very similar effect to mechanical performance of the materials as it is the case for KOH solution. Test results and literature investigations made it obvious that PPS GF30 is not an option for the application. Additionally, it became clear that alkaline resistant fibers have other issues concerning bonding in the matrix.

A newly developed Tedur PPS grade with a special KOH/NaOH resistant filler showed stable behavior at 90°C in 30% NaOH over 672 hours without decreasing mechanical performance in terms of E-modulus, tensile strength, elongation at break, and even Charpy unnotched impact performance. This was not the case for PPS with glass fiber, which showed continuous degradation performance. The new Tedur L PPS 4030 NC1049-24 compound enables the production of an AWE frame as a 1K solution with comprehensive cost reduction potential of up to 40% in raw material while expecting to providing better creep performance. Up to 50% less raw material costs can be achieved using a 2K solution by selecting a

material for media contact combined with a co-injectable, chemically bondable material like a highly filled PPS compound with glass fibers and minerals.

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